

Requirements Analysis Report 2024

Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for NFDI

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1. ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics
2. TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology - University Library
3. Mannheim University Library
4. FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure
5. GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
6. ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences
7. Deutsche Nationalbibliothek

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Project KGI4NFDI
Work Package 4 Community Support
Deliverable D4.1 Survey of existing KG adoption practices in NFDI

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Introduction

KGI4NFDI who?

KGI4NFDI aims to channel the Knowledge Graph (KG) adoption initiatives across NFDI consortia, by providing support for (i) access and exploration of the KGs, and (ii) KG adoption – creation for the different communities in the NFDI. In order to understand the requirements for KG adoption and any related practices, we needed to conduct a landscape analysis. Thus, we chose the survey as the appropriate approach to complete this feat.

Survey aim

With this survey, we targeted members with different positions/roles across the NFDI consortia and their experience with the topic of knowledge graphs in their consortia or institutions. The initial sample included members either involved in a specific capacity on this topic, or, when this information was not available, the corresponding contact persons of the consortia. This also included sharing the survey via different NFDI Working Groups related to the topic, or directly to our professional networks. We contacted the members with an explanation of the survey goals, while encouraging them to share the survey invitation with colleagues that fit the survey target, just in case the invitation did not reach them.

The survey ran from December 5 to December 31, 2024, with the possibility for more than one participant per NFDI consortium/institution to participate. Overall, the survey had 81 participants, which we assess as a satisfactory step towards understanding the KG adoption practices for these communities.

The survey consisted of 21 questions, grouped according to three key themes:

- (i) basic information of the survey participants;
- (ii) the type of data and use cases that KGs are/could be employed to address for a consortium; and
- (iii) an invitation the participant to provide additional aspects of interest to the topic, including their readiness to participate in a follow up interview.

Survey theme	Obligation & Type
General information	
1. What is the name of the institution you represent?	Mandatory
2. Which NFDI consortia are you involved in?	Optional; Multiple selection
3. What is your role in your institution/consortium?	Optional; Multiple selection
4. Please specify your role:	Conditional
Data and use cases	
5. What kinds of data do you deal with during your tasks?	Optional; Multiple selection
6. Please explain the data in terms of domain, schema, format, etc.	Conditional
7. Have you encountered Knowledge Graphs in your work environment before this survey?	Optional; Single selection
8. Do you already provide or plan to provide a Knowledge Graph at your institution/consortium?	Optional; Single selection
9. Separate KG links with comma, if multiple.	Conditional
10. If you already provide/adopt a Knowledge Graph at your institution/consortium, what objectives does it support?	Optional; Multiple selection
11. Please specify	Conditional

12. If you already provide/adopt a Knowledge Graph at your institution/consortium, what challenges have been faced in implementing it?	Optional; Multiple selection
13. Please specify	Conditional
14. How can the Knowledge Graph Infrastructure Base service support you with your current Knowledge Graph activities or future plans?	Optional; Multiple selection
15. Please specify	Conditional
16. Do you plan to connect your (meta)data with other NFDI consortia?	Optional; Single selection
17. What is the rationale for this?	Optional
18. What are the reasons for this (privacy/regulation, lack of use cases, etc.)?	Optional
Conclusion	
19. If you would like to provide any additional relevant information that we did not ask in the survey, please feel free to do so.	Optional
20. May we contact you in case we have further questions?	Optional
21. Please give name and email address, separated by a comma:	Conditional

Table 1. The KGI survey

Given the specifics of the topic and trying to gather as much feedback as possible, we opted for a minimal set of mandatory questions, leaving the participant with options to provide any feedback they had, even if minimal or in a planning stage.

Survey analysis

When analyzing the survey results, we focused on a few aspects - and the corresponding questions – across the three key themes of the survey. Since the theme of “data and use cases” takes the better part of the survey, we will reflect this in the analysis as well. For every question, we indicate its obligation in the survey (mandatory, optional), and type (single vs multiple selection; the rest are text-based questions). Additionally, for the optional questions we also indicate if they depend on previous answers to display them to the participant (noted as “conditional” in the Table 1). For any reference to the survey questions, we will use the letter “Q” and the number that refers to the question (refer to Table 1 above).

Figure 1. Participants' roles

General information

All but five NFDI consortia had at least one participant in the survey; on the other hand, there were cases with seven participants from a single consortium. When it comes to the roles (Q3), two of the largest groups of participants involve software engineers/developers and researchers at different levels; the “other” group of roles included co-PI, Service Provider, Group Leader, and Senior Manager, whereas those that identified themselves as “Researchers” included post-doctoral and PhD researchers (Figure 1). Our aim was to include different roles across NFDI consortia: while software developers or knowledge engineers are typically

those working with KGs, getting stakeholder support for KG adoption from other roles in a consortium is also important.

Data and use cases

Data structure On the topic of the structure of the data in use (Q5), based on the answers from 70% of the participants, there is a relatively balanced mix between structured (schema-based, organized, stored in a database), semi-structured (XML, JSON files, etc.) and unstructured (text, video, audio, etc.) data. It will be interesting to monitor how this trend will unfold, especially with regard to the unstructured data.

If the participants preferred, they could also describe the data in terms of the domain, schema or other features (Q6), and not necessarily based on the structure. To this end, one participant mentioned geodata-like shape files according to the GeoTiff¹ metadata standard. Lastly, 42 answers (not shown in Figure 2) were not sure about this question.

Figure 2. The structure of the data

Figure 3. Familiarity with KGs

KG familiarity From the 50% of the participants that answered this question (Fig. 3), 83% did encounter KGs in their activities (Q7). Related to this, we wanted to know about actual KG adoption projects across the NFDI consortia (Q8). From the 50% of the participants that answered the question, 32% already do or plan to adopt a KG, 7% do not, and 10% are not sure about it (section A of the Appendix provides the reported existing or planned KGs in different communities).

Figure 4. KG objectives

From those already providing a Knowledge Graph at their institution/consortium (Q10), the top objective is data integration, followed by single point of access, and research data management (Fig. 4). The application of AI is another objective, which we plan to follow up on during the interview phase later in the project. Finally, in addition to these four objectives, participants also mention:

- Providing OAI PMH records for the records.
- Providing machine-actionable semantic data access to users
- Providing an open, customizable and FAIR data endpoint for specialized users of our resources.
- Provide a SPARQL endpoint and Schema.org annotation on dataset landing pages (enabling harvesting by search engines such as Google Dataset Search etc.).

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GeoTiff>

- Evaluation of journal metrics; providing journal users with information on suitable reviewers or relevant publications;
- Comparison of criteria for different long-term energy system scenarios.

There are a few challenges related to adopting a KG (Q12): 27% of the participants report “resource heterogeneity” (in terms of schema description, representation, etc.) as the key challenge, followed by “record linking” (17%), “deduplication” (17%), and lack of mature open source solutions to implement KGs (11%). Another 11% of the participants point out at challenges such as converting raw data to RDF and lack of educational materials, managing expectations from implementing KGs, applying KGs to emerging requirements such as FAIR Digital Objects, as well as convincing stakeholders from fields other than Computer Science on the benefits of KGs.

KG support As part of the requirements gathering for KGI4NFDI, and to better plan the current and future services in the project, we were interested to know how the KGI could support existing KGs or those planning to adopt one (Q14). The majority of the participants require support for “Data integration and import”, which matches with the top objective for KG adoption reported in the survey (Q10). Currently, some of the support that participants mention we already offer (searching for other KGs and consulting, for example), whereas some we are considering for the Integration phase of the project, especially consulting and hosting. Fig. 5 contains all the details.

Figure 5. Support for KG adoption

Finally, the participants that did not would also want support with the following requirements (from the “other” option):

- Integration of entities from different Knowledge Graphs
- Tools to simplify the generation and exploration of KG that can be used by scientists without extensive KG training
- Harmonisation of ontologies and KGs
- Interoperability of KGs across consortium boundaries to enable federated queries
- Extensive comparison of open source-based approaches (on a technical level)
- Benchmarks for the various technical (implementation) options

As a last question of this section, we wanted to know if the community aims to connect to other NFDI consortia (Q16). From the 50% of the participants that answered this question, the majority intends to do so, whereas 17% currently do not; additionally, 2% are unsure about this question (see Fig. 6).

Figure 6 Connecting your (meta)data with other NFDI consortia

For those that responded with “Yes” to this question, they were asked to provide a rationale for such a need, which resulted with 23 requirements, with standardization, FAIR publication of data, data reuse across consortia (in line with the One NFDI vision) being but few of these requirements; section B of the Appendix provides the complete list of these requirements.

Survey conclusion

In the last section of the survey, we wanted to know about additional related information that the participants could share, including the possibility of meeting with us to discuss on these topics.

Relevant information feedback we missed Due to the relatively broad coverage of roles and consortia, we tried to keep the survey in more generic, meaning the questions were meant to elicit some initial insights about current practices or KG adoption plans across the NFDI. We reserved this question to capture additional information that is applicable only to a small group of consortia/survey participants. 9% of the participants suggested additional information, including:

- AI application for KGs
- Example KGs, including information on the different KG creation phases. Related to this, development and hosting for a successful KGI4NFDI.
- Visual interfaces to KGs for the less experienced users
- Cross-KG linking across the consortia

Would you be interested to meet with us? A quantitative technique such as the survey has its limitations. To complement it with a qualitative one, we planned an interview so that we can follow up with the participants that have more to say on the topics covered in the survey, and more. Another reason for planning the interviews has to do with the next, Integration phase of the KGI4NFDI. As part of this phase, we plan to have incubator projects during which interested NFDI members can receive guidance and support towards adopting a KG. As indicated in the last question of the survey, twenty-eight percent of the participants expressed their interest in participating in an interview.

Conclusion

This survey helped us establish an initial understanding on the current practices and prospects of KG adoptions across different NFDI consortia and communities. In trying to be more inclusive across different roles in NFDI consortia, we kept the level of details low so that more participants could answer most of the questions.

Twenty eight percent (22 in total) of the participants shared their interest in having a follow up interview. Based on this, we plan to explore some of the objectives and challenges NFDI consortia members face in their journey to KG adoption, as well as the potential support that KGI4NFDI could provide in this context.

Appendix

Considering that the survey tool did not have text proofing feature, we slightly edited the answers for eventual typos and small rewrites, in line with the original content.

A) Existing Knowledge Graphs or plans to adopt one

- Dokumentationsplattform des Standardisierungsausschusses: [Link](#) to the query interface
- Plan to provide a Knowledge Graph describing and connecting datasets and software with other information entities like articles, projects, methods, actors, tools.
- The Data Collections Explorer project: <https://github.com/kit-data-manager/Data-Collections-Explorer-Graph>
- The DBLP Computer Science Bibliography: <https://sparql.dblp.org/>
- Digital Resources of the Leibniz Institute DSMZ: <https://sparql.dsmz.de/>
- 4Culture-KG, 4Memory-KG, 4Chem Semantic Hub, RADAR(-Cloud, -4Culture, -4Chem, -4Memory) KG
- Open Energy Family - Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG):
<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oekg>,
https://openenergyplatform.github.io/organisation/family_members/knowledge-representation/oekg/, https://openenergyplatform.org/sparql_query/sparql
- There is no pool of KGs available for the discipline, but we want to embed info from chemical ontologies.
- Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration: <https://search.unhide.helmholtz-metadaten.de/>,
<https://sparql.unhide.helmholtz-metadaten.de/>
- NFDI-MatWerk: <https://msekg-nfdi-matwerk-02.web.vulcanus.otc.coscine.dev/matwerk/>
- GESIS KG, TweetsKB, TweetsCov19, ClaimsKG, GESIS Datasearch KG, Software KG, SoMeSci, Thesaurus for the Social Sciences
- MethodsHub KG, KG of AI and DS methods, GSAP KG (Planned)
- Based on The Photon and Neutron Experimental Techniques Ontology: <https://expands-eu.github.io/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology/index-en.html>; NeXusOntology: <https://github.com/nexusformat/NeXusOntology> (Planned)
- MethodsHub KG, KG of AI and DS methods, GSAP KG (In progress)
- NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub: <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/>
- Open Math Research Data MaRDI: <https://portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>, <https://mathalgotdb.mardi4nfdi.de/>,
<https://morwiki.mpi-magdeburg.mpg.de/>, <https://portal.mardi4nfdi.de/wiki/MathModDB>

B) Connecting the (meta)data with those in other NFDI consortia

- Connecting a large database with occurrence data, georeferenced, with abiotic data
- Biodiversity and land use, biodiversity and agriculture, biodiversity and health....

- Standardisation
- Share the GND authority files in a FAIR way with the whole NFDI and beyond.
- This is the main goal of the NFDI ("One NFDI")
- Engineering science is based on a number of other sciences, especially mathematics and natural sciences and offers application cases for many different domains. So the information entities relevant for engineering sciences are also relevant in other disciplines and there is a need to map/integrate/reuse them.
- Make data FAIR
- Increased interoperability
- Maximal accessibility of training materials
- Scientific question is relevant across scientific disciplines
- We are a data provider, and connecting, opening and sharing data is our whole business
- One NFDI
- Harmonised access, interoperability, interdisciplinarity
- Biodata Interest Group
- Consortia use same methods - metadata should be the same as well
- Findability across disciplines
- Especially in the humanities, data sources are often of interest to more than just one consortium.
- Plans of metadata harvesting
- Catalysis is interdisciplinary.
- Increasing usage, visibility and accessibility of our data to support and facilitate interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary use cases
- Testing and providing interoperability with other disciplines
- Cross-domain data linking; increasing usage, visibility and accessibility of our data to support and facilitate interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary use cases
- One NFDI
- Mathematical modelling is used in many fields and thus many NFDI consortia